

Several factors could be responsible for these differences, including the fact that definitions and practices in this area vary and the units studied have ranged from forensic wards to general psychiatric wards.

Incidents seemed more likely to happen at times of interaction with staff (e.g. mealtimes and the medication round), possibly owing to the increased potential for confrontation.² Staffing numbers were possibly 'adequate' as, despite common agreement that high staff-patient ratios are an integral part of PICU provision, this ratio has not been precisely defined.

As suggested by the Royal College of Psychiatrists,⁵ de-escalation techniques were the most used interventions and were tried first in most instances. Figure 2 shows that a hierarchy of techniques was used, progressing from the least to the most invasive interventions whenever possible.

The relatively high levels of seclusion on this unit could be explained by the lack of any intermediate facility between an open ward environment and seclusion, such as time-out or de-escalation rooms, or access to bedrooms. Another contributing factor may have been the stringent definition used on the unit, as suggested by the Royal College

of Psychiatrists: 'seclusion should include occasions when the door is open or unlocked and when the patients are locked in their rooms overnight'.⁶

Although not formally assessed, a temporary move to new premises with a more favourable physical setting appeared to decrease rates of disturbed behaviour. Other studies have found similar trends.⁸⁻¹⁰

Conclusions

This area requires a coherent approach across PICUs and the use of a unified approach to recording and managing incidents of disturbed behaviour, as this could provide the necessary overview to refine existing practice. We recommend that all units use the integrated approach recommended by the Royal College of Psychiatrists' guidelines.^{5,6}

Future research in this area should incorporate environmental factors as well as staffing issues. This would facilitate a joined up approach to policy development and patient management in PICUs.

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Impact of the European Working Time Directive on an epistaxis service

Usama F Kamel¹ and Dimitrios Chatzoudis¹

¹Staff ENT Surgeon, ENT Department, Gwynedd Hospital, Bangor LL57 2PW, email ufkamel@aol.com; ²Senior House Officer, ENT Department, Gwynedd Hospital, Bangor, Wales

- The European Working Time Directive (EWTD) may have had a detrimental effect on the ability to manage common ear, nose and throat (ENT) emergencies.
- Inter-departmental cross-cover has not been shown to be cost-effective.
- More resources and training are needed to implement the EWTD appropriately.

Epistaxis is considered one of the commonest emergencies in ENT.¹ In the UK, hospital management

of epistaxis is usually performed by junior medical staff in accident and emergency or ENT departments.²

After the EWTD was implemented in August 2004, a new inter-departmental cross-cover system was introduced in many hospitals. This resulted in 60% of night shifts (8 p.m. - 8 a.m.) being covered by the orthopaedic senior house officers (SHOs) in our hospital.

Lack of training or experience as a result of EWTD implementation has been previously highlighted.³

The objective of the study was to determine the influence of the cross-cover of the orthopaedic SHOs on the management of epistaxis. Data were compared with a previous departmental audit conducted from January to July 2004, when the department was entirely covered by ENT trainees and staff.

Methods

We conducted a retrospective analysis of epistaxis patients admitted

Figure 1. Reasons for admission of patients with epistaxis before (service provided by ENT SHOs) and after (service provided by cross-cover) the introduction of the European Working Time Directive.

to hospital between September 2004 and March 2005.

The SHOs had at their disposal most of the commonly used materials for epistaxis management: for nose packing, tampons, gauze, bismuth iodoform paraffin paste (BIPP), Brighton balloons and Foley's catheters; for nasal cauterisation, silver nitrate sticks and electrocautery. All admitted patients had a minimum of full blood count and coagulation screen tests.

Results

Sixty-two patients (31 males, 31 females) were admitted to hospital over the seven-month study period. The age range was 4–91 years (previous audit 6–99 years). The average age for males was 55 years and for females 66 years. Fifty-seven patients were admitted once (91%), four patients were admitted twice (6.4%) and one patient was admitted three times.

On admission, only 36 patients (58%) were actively bleeding, compared with 88% in the previous audit. Other reasons for admission in this study were: associated medical problems in 31% (19 patients), compared with 10% in the previous audit; admission for observation without any active intervention in five patients (8%); and social reasons in one patient (1.6%) (Figure 1).

Other associated medical problems revealed that 36% of patients were on warfarin (compared with 28% in the previous audit), 28% had high blood pressure (67% in the previous

audit), 15% had head injury (5% in the previous audit), 5% had anaemia, 5% had recent rhinoplasty, 5% had dysphagia and 5% had tonsillar hypertrophy.

With regard to treatment, 69% of patients in the present audit (43 patients) were cauterised with silver nitrate sticks and 6% (4 patients) had electrocautery. In total, cautery was applied in 75% of the patients (83% in the previous audit). Nasal cauterisation was successful in 62% of patients, which was lower than expected.⁴

Thirty-seven patients (60%) were packed anteriorly, which was similar to the previous audit (57%). Merocel tampons were used in 42% of patients, compared with 14% previously. BIPP and Vaseline packs were used in 5% and 11% of cases, respectively (8% and 13% previously). Finally, Kaltostat packs were used in 8% before the introduction of the cross-cover system, but none since the introduction of the EWTD.

The use of the posterior packs – Brighton balloons – had decreased from 11% previously to 5%. No patients required blood transfusion.

Duration of hospital stay and number of admissions

Of the total 62 patients examined, 5 (8%) were discharged on the same day and 57 (92%) were admitted for one or more days: 18 (32%) for one day, 10 for two days (18%), 15 (27%) for three days, 10 (18%) for four days and 4 (6%) for five days or more. The average hospital stay in this study was 2.6 days.

After considering the above results, more teaching sessions and protocols were introduced to orthopaedic SHOs.

Discussion

In our study, the patient admission threshold had been reduced significantly in comparison with the period before the introduction of the EWTD, leading to 92% of the referred patients staying in hospital. Of these, only 58% were actively bleeding on admission.

Orthopaedic SHOs prefer to use handy materials, such as Merocel tampons, but avoid nasal cauterisation. However, more consumption of materials (Merocel packs) was noted. Although patients were admitted unnecessarily, this did not affect the overall patient hospitalisation, as it seemed to have reduced the readmission rate.

Some hospitals apply cover between departments for reasons of cost-effectiveness. In our study, this appeared to have had the opposite effect, as our departmental occupancy had been increased. The limitation of training and competence since the EWTD implementation has been highlighted in many articles.⁵ We have here documented the effect on patient management and resources. We became more convinced that the EWTD benefited neither patients nor surgeons. The EWTD may have had a detrimental effect on our ability to manage common ENT emergencies, such as epistaxis.

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